

Technologies for IMINT and SIGINT

Domenico Frascà
Research Department
Zanasi & Partners
Modena, Italy

domenico.frasca@zanasi-alessandro.eu

Giulia Venturi
Research Department
Zanasi & Partners
Modena, Italy

giulia.venturi@zanasi-alessandro.eu

Maria Ustenko
Research Department
Zanasi & Partners
Modena, Italy

maria.ustenko@zanasi-alessandro.eu

Alessandro Zanasi
President
Zanasi & Partners
Modena, Italy

alessandro.zanasi@zanasi-alessandro.eu

Abstract—This work reports up-to-date information about the latest technological developments in Imagery Intelligence (IMINT) and Signals Intelligence (SIGINT) within the Euro-Atlantic community. The work is based on the outcomes of the NOTIONES “iNteracting netwOrk of inTelligence and securITy practitiOners with iNdustry and acadEmia actorS” project, which is funded under the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme. Nowadays Intelligence technologies are no longer the sole prerogative of National Intelligence agencies and Law Enforcement Agencies. To the contrary, there is a commercial proliferation of IMINT and SIGINT technologies and tools. The paper deals with different methods, means and technologies used for Imagery Intelligence activities, with particular emphasis on IMINT capabilities of airborne and space platforms such as manned aircrafts, UASs, HAPSs, and imaging satellites. For Signals Intelligence the paper shares insights of the different subfields of this Intelligence discipline: Electronic Intelligence (ELINT) and Communication Intelligence (COMINT). The purpose of this review of technologies and tools is to facilitate the discussion among Intelligence and Security practitioners, the academic world and the technology providers, with the final goal of expressing clear requirements and recommendations about future research lines and development objectives.

Keywords— *COMINT, ELINT, IMINT, Intelligence Collection, SIGINT, Technologies*

I. INTRODUCTION

This research article is focused on providing up-to-date information about the latest technological developments in Imagery Intelligence (IMINT) and Signals Intelligence (SIGINT) within the Euro-Atlantic community, as well as insights on the relevance and applicability of these technologies for the Intelligence communities (IC) and law enforcement agencies (LEAs). A critical part of the Intelligence Cycle is collecting raw information needed to produce finished Intelligence through several Intelligence disciplines, including IMINT and SIGINT [1]. Intelligence collection capabilities are often limited by the technological capabilities of the Intelligence agencies. Historically, less technologically capable Nations have been unable to gain access to information; however, this situation has recently changed. Indeed, there is a proliferation of IMINT and SIGINT technologies and platforms around the world, including even relatively inexpensive and portable Unmanned Aircraft Systems (UASs), which are becoming available to a wide variety of users and organisations. Commercial Imagery

products that approach the quality of Intelligence collection systems are becoming more readily available on the free market. Meanwhile, the developments in artificial intelligence (AI) and image analysis software enable efficient results according to the Intelligence needs [2].

Depending on how various organisations define their Intelligence Cycles, IMINT and SIGINT may also contain some analysis processes of the collected data, but it is quite uncommon, as they primarily focus on gathering raw information [3].

Intelligence operations are traditionally conducted by national organisations, but there are cases of structured collaboration between multiple Countries and/or agencies at a supranational and international level. The so-called Five Eyes (FVEY) is an Intelligence alliance comprising Australia, Canada, New Zealand, the United Kingdom, and the United States [4]. Within the EU framework, the Single Intelligence Analysis Capacity (SIAC) – which combines the European Union Intelligence Analysis Centre (EU INTCEN) and the European Union Military Staff (EUMS) – produces Intelligence analysis based on information from the civilian and military Intelligence agencies of all the EU Member States [5]. As the main international agencies for Law Enforcement operating in the Euro-Atlantic community, both Europol and Interpol conduct Intelligence activities in their efforts to combat various forms of cybercrime, organised crime, and terrorism [6][7]. Finally, the North Atlantic Treaty Organization (NATO) Fusion Centre (NIFC) provides the Supreme Headquarters Allied Powers Europe (SHAPE) and the Allied Command Operations (ACO) with relevant and accurate Intelligence to support the planning and execution of NATO operations [8]. Moreover, under the NATO Communications and Information Agency (NCIA), the Alliance has established a permanent Joint Intelligence, Surveillance and Recognition (JISR) system that provides Intelligence products to decision-makers of all NATO Armed Forces, Member States and Partners [9]. JISR brings together raw information collected through platforms of different initiatives such as NATO Alliance Ground Surveillance (AGS) [10] or NATO Airborne Warning and Control System (AWACS) [11], as well as a wide variety of national Intelligence, Surveillance, and Reconnaissance (ISR) assets from the land, maritime, air and space domains. It is to be noted that, on 15 February 2023, a group of 17 NATO Allies, together with invitee Sweden, announced plans to launch the

Alliance Persistent Surveillance from Space (APSS) initiative, which will transform the way NATO collects and uses data from the space domain, in order to improve NATO's Intelligence collection and thus better provide essential support to the Alliance's military missions and operations [12].

TABLE I. SUPRANATIONAL AND INTERNATIONAL COOPERATIONS ON INTELLIGENCE

Type	Cooperation
Military	Five Eyes (FVEY) – Australia, Canada, New Zealand, the United Kingdom, and the United States
Civilian and military	EU Single Intelligence Analysis Capacity (SIAC) – European Union Intelligence Analysis Centre (EU INTCEN) and European Union Military Staff (EUMS)
Civilian	Europol and Interpol
Military	North Atlantic Treaty Organization (NATO) Fusion Centre (NIFC)
Military	NATO Joint Intelligence, Surveillance and Recognition (JISR) system
Military	NATO Alliance Persistent Surveillance from Space (APSS) initiative

Intelligence collection systems are being developed in all operating environments. Intelligence communities and LEAs make use of several methods, platforms, and technological solutions to perform their mission.

This work deals with different methods, means and technologies used for Imagery Intelligence activities, with particular emphasis on IMINT capabilities of airborne and space platforms such as manned aircrafts, UASs, high-altitude platform system (HAPSs), and imaging satellites. For Signals Intelligence this work shares insights of the different subfields of this Intelligence discipline: Electronic Intelligence (ELINT) and Communication Intelligence (COMINT). ELINT deals with the interception of radio waves, radio pulses, and other radio signals from radars, missiles and guidance systems, etc. in order to identify and monitor enemies or potential threats. ELINT means the interception of “non-communication” signals – not voice or text. Much of COMINT's current activity is related to the interception of fixed, mobile and Internet communications. From an ethical and legal perspective, SIGINT activities may involve a trade-off between personal freedom and collective security – i.e., the issue of lawful interception.

Regarding SIGINT, it should be noted that it belongs traditionally to the military domain and those Intelligence agencies which deal with foreign signals and external threats to national security. In this context, the state-of-the-art in SIGINT technologies and methodologies has always been highly classified.

II. IMAGERY INTELLIGENCE

The definition of Imagery Intelligence is not identical within the Euro-Atlantic community. Many Countries consider it a sub-category of Geospatial Intelligence

(GEOINT) [13]; some organisations consider it an Intelligence gathering activity only from air and space platforms [14], while others do include land-based and naval means [15]. In order to be as general and inclusive as possible, this paper will use the definitions provided by NATO and the European Defence Agency (EDA) [16]: “*Imagery Intelligence is the technical, geographic and Intelligence information derived through the interpretation or analysis of imagery and collateral materials. It includes exploitation of imagery data derived from several category of sensors: electro-optical (EO), radar, infrared (IR), multi-spectral or laser. IMINT is collected via satellites, unmanned aerial vehicles (UAVs), reconnaissance aircrafts and ground systems*”. In broad terms, Imagery Intelligence is derived from the exploitation of collected images – by visual photography, infrared sensors, lasers, electro-optics, and radar sensors – wherein the images are reproduced optically or electronically on film, electronic display devices, or other media.

Imagery Intelligence is closely linked to other Intelligence disciplines, like Geospatial Intelligence (GEOINT), Open-Source Intelligence (OSINT), Measurement and Signature Intelligence (MASINT), and Mass Surveillance. Depending on the Intelligence requirements, IMINT can be used for assessing the situation, the evolution of the situation, accurately detecting and identifying targets, evaluating the associated risks and the effectiveness of an action undertaken both for military and civil circumstances [17]. Within the Intelligence Cycle, nowadays IMINT often has an ever-increasing role in assessing situations autonomously. This is due to recent trends in Earth Observation (EO), which is the general term used to refer to the collection and analysis of information about Earth's physical, chemical, and biological systems via remote sensing technologies, usually involving satellites carrying imaging devices, as well as aerial platforms – e.g., airplanes, helicopters, and unmanned aerial vehicles (UAVs) [18]. Imagery Intelligence can be collected from many platforms operating in different operational domains, but airborne and spaceborne platforms are the most important and versatile.

Spaceborne platforms – i.e., imaging satellites – have historically been government-owned and have produced highly reliable and secure information. However, since the early 2000s commercial satellite imagery providers have emerged with industry-owned satellites acquiring images at very high resolution (VHR), providing much more spatial details than government-owned satellites available for civilian applications. The growth of commercial imaging satellites has accelerated in recent years, with the emergence of CubeSat constellations providing more frequent and cost-effective VHR imagery [19]. Intelligence and defence are application areas of satellite imagery, among others – e.g., geospatial data acquisition and mapping, natural resource management, surveillance and security, construction and development, conservation and research, and disaster management [20].

The main criteria for assessing the capabilities of spaceborne platforms are spatial resolution relative to targets; revisit frequency; imaging capability anywhere in the world; and video acquisition ability – from very short ones up to 1 to 3 minutes, due to orbital constraints. Capabilities of satellite imagery have also begun to be developed through the increasingly powerful development of machine learning (ML) and AI capabilities. For instance, specific AI algorithms could be digitally uploaded to processors on some of the Earth

Observation satellites already in orbit without any ground assistance. This would make it possible to transform even low-cost commercial satellites into spy platforms capable of tracking even moving targets as small as a car size [21].

Airborne imagery refers to images and videos taken from an aerial perspective. Airborne platforms consist of manned, unmanned, fixed wing, and rotary aircrafts, as well as balloons and HAPSs [22]. Significantly, in the last decade, drones have assumed a central role in carrying out Intelligence activities. Depending on the type and model of the aerial imagery system, the flight height varies. Intelligence, Surveillance and Reconnaissance (ISR) payload – e.g., sensors, cameras, and radars – mounted on airplanes, drones, balloons, or HAPSs are chosen according to the needs of the mission and can generally provide persistent coverage of a location or target for a given time [23]. The choice for the capability depends on the mission requirements: spatial resolution relative to targets, how frequently information is needed, or maximum ISR payload that can be carried – e.g., instruments onboard Class I and II UASs are quite limited in size and weight [24].

IMINT technologies that can be mounted on aerial platforms or satellites include optical sensors, synthetic aperture radars (SARs), thermal imaging, and light detection and ranging (LiDAR). The type of resolution is also very important. Each sensor type offers advantages in observing certain targets or phenomena, and often a combination of different sensors from different platforms is needed to properly analyse and provide meaningful insights about a given situation on the ground surface. This type of data processing is called data fusion – e.g., the combination of EO data acquired by different sensors on various platforms which may have different spatial, spectral, and temporal resolutions [25]. The fusion of different types of collected Intelligence can provide a more comprehensive situational awareness.

TABLE II. TECHNOLOGIES FOR IMINT

Spaceborne and Airborne Platforms
Optical sensors – e.g., microwaves, infrared, visible light, ultraviolet light
Synthetic aperture radars (SARs)
Thermal imaging tools
Light detection and ranging (LiDAR)

III. SIGNALS INTELLIGENCE

Signals Intelligence is another Intelligence Collection discipline. The Official NATO Terminology Database defines SIGINT as “*Intelligence derived from electromagnetic signals or emissions*”, noting that the main subcategories of Signals Intelligence are Communications Intelligence and Electronic Intelligence, depending on whether it comes from communications between people or from electronic signals not directly used in communication [26]. COMINT targets voice and teleprinter traffic, video, Morse code traffic, or even facsimile messages. Assuming access is possible, Communications Intelligence can be collected from air waves, cables, fibre optics, or any other transmission medium. ELINT includes the interception of non-communications transmissions such as radars [27]. Although classified, in 2016 NATO published the Allied Joint Doctrine for Signals

Intelligence (AJP-2.4), demonstrating the existence of a shared conception of SIGINT within the Atlantic Alliance [28].

Signal Intelligence activities are historically carried out by military Intelligence to estimate and prevent foreign and external threats to national security. In the strictest sense, one of the most important SIGINT tasks is to determine the Electronic Order of Battle (EOB), i.e., the localisation and identification of radars and communications nodes associated with enemy weapons systems, and the networks in the enemy territory [29]. However, in recent decades LEAs have been increasingly using advanced technological means to carry out their mission focusing on crime prevention and investigations – not necessarily related to foreign or external threats. Some of these means fit in with the SIGINT definition of intercepting signals.

It should be pointed out that the methods of intercepting communication signals or data may violate privacy rights: therefore, there are continuously court cases on the circumstances of using telecommunications or signals interception. Discussions on current legislation are also regular, both on national and supranational level. Indeed, SIGINT activities may involve a trade-off between personal freedom and collective security [30].

A long-standing problem in SIGINT is recognising new types of signals, such as those from RF-controlled threats – e.g., UAVs or improvised explosive devices (IEDs) [31]. Signals Intelligence collection can be performed from a variety of assets operating in several operational domains – e.g., ground, ship, submarine, aerial and satellite platforms – through advanced electronic Intelligence equipment, with both COMINT and ELINT capabilities. In particular, manned and unmanned ISR aircrafts with advanced SIGINT capabilities are very widespread and play a critical role in Intelligence collection [32].

On all these SIGINT platforms, ELINT focuses its attention on radar systems and on the analysis of their characteristics, or more generally on radio frequency (RF) signals not related to communications [33]. In order to do this, an ELINT system must detect and locate radars in a specific area and monitor the full electronic spectrum of interest – far away from enemy installations. An ELINT system must also provide detailed information and parameters of enemy radars. Modern radars use a wide variety of signal waveforms such as pulses, pulse-Doppler, frequency hopping (FH), frequency and pulse coding, and so on. Taking these factors into account, an ELINT system must have both broadband panoramic receivers for monitoring the environment and selective superheterodyne receivers for measuring radar waveforms [34].

The original purpose of military COMINT was to intercept enemy radio communications. Today this also includes the interception of fixed, mobile and Internet communications, which is of interest to LEAs as well [35]. In hybrid warfare, the Internet itself is weaponised in the form of viruses, distributed denial-of-service (DDoS) attacks, intrusions, and sabotage programmes, or generally providing false information in an attempt to influence public opinion [36]. Signals-wise COMINT aims to catch the RF parameters, like carrier frequencies, bandwidths, and modulation types, as well as the information exchanged between users or terminals.

Phone monitoring can be divided into two categories: physical and mobile. Physical runs on the Public Switched Telephone Network (PSTN, or landline), while mobile runs on wireless radio networks – which are the mainstream these days [37]. Companies manufacturing the base stations and other hardware for mobile radio networks also sell mobile traffic monitoring systems for network operators. Law enforcement agencies and Intelligence bodies can obtain these data in some cases – lawful interception (LI) of communications. Depending on the legal system of a given Country, this may, for instance, require LEAs to provide a probable cause of criminal activity to obtain a court order to request mobile telecommunications data from a network operator or gain access to a legal interception gateway or node [38]. Mobile telecommunications can also be intercepted passively in between the mobile device and the base station it is communicating with. A well-known interception tool is the Stingray system, also known as GSM interceptor or International Mobile Subscriber Identity (IMSI) catcher [39].

Intercepting Internet communications can be physical, or software-based. Physical involves installing interception hardware – e.g., wire taps and fibre optic splices – in the fibre optic network or the routers, repeaters, and the like in the network [40]. There have been plans in Europe to require the network operators to install interception interfaces for lawful interception. This is similar to the case in some Countries where the law requires mobile network operators to install legal interception gateways (LIGs) or legal interception nodes (LINs) [41]. These types of methods usually refer to network-type Mass Surveillance scenarios. An example of software-based Internet interception is intercepting encrypted web traffic between the web browser and the website with an interceptor software [42].

TABLE III. TECHNOLOGIES FOR SIGINT

ELINT and COMINT
Panoramic receivers
Superheterodyne receivers
GSM interceptors/ IMSI catchers
Interception hardware – e.g., wire taps, fibre optic splices
Software-based tools for intercepting Internet communications

IV. CONCLUSIONS

Due to rapid technological advances, maintaining performance requires continuous and relevant new investments. Recent technology trends, as well as the significant increase in the amount of available information – including irrelevant information – and the complexity of analysis, place demands on the development of Intelligence processes and systems to provide end-to-end information that is relevant and useful to the decision-makers. The long-term development of personnel skills is also important. Both IMINT and SIGINT provide important sources of Intelligence information in multi-Intelligence platforms. With the aid of current and future AI and ML capabilities, these platforms will conceptually transform and impact traditional methods to process Intelligence. Future Intelligence will rely on technology, data fusion and analysis of multiple Intelligence

sources where IMINT and SIGINT technologies provide an important baseline for the collection of data and information on relevant targets and missions.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

This work was supported by the project NOTIONES, that has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101021853.

The objective of the NOTIONES (*iNteracting netwOrk of iTelligence and securITy practitiOners with iNdustry and acadEmia actorS*) project is to build a pan-European network of practitioners from the security and intelligence services, from the Industry – including SMEs – and from the Academia, with the objective to enhance their interaction and identify specific technology and innovation requirements, needs, expectations and gaps.

REFERENCES

- [1] NATO Terminology Office. Intelligence Cycle. NATO Term (Official NATO Terminology Database). <https://nso.nato.int/natoterm/content/nato/pages/home.html?lg=en> [Accessed: 25/06/2023].
- [2] Vegavid Technology. The Power of AI in Image Processing: A Comprehensive Guide. Vegavid Technology. <https://vegavid.com/blog/power-of-ai-in-image-processing/> [Accessed: 25/06/2023].
- [3] US Office of the Director of National Intelligence (2013). US National Intelligence: An Overview (2013). US Office of the Director of National Intelligence. https://www.dni.gov/files/documents/USNI%202013%20Overview_web.pdf [Accessed: 25/06/2023].
- [4] Five Eyes Intelligence Oversight and Review Council (2017). Charter of the Five Eyes Intelligence Oversight and Review Council. US Office of the Director of National Intelligence. <https://www.dni.gov/files/ICIG/Documents/Partnerships/FIORC/Signed%20FIORC%20Charter%20with%20Line.pdf> [Accessed: 25/06/2023].
- [5] European Union External Action (2019). Impetus 28, Magazine of the EU Military Staff, EEAS, Brussels – Autumn/Winter 2019, Issue 28. European Union External Action. https://www.eeas.europa.eu/sites/default/files/documents/eums_impetus_28_final_web.pdf [Accessed: 25/06/2023].
- [6] Europol (07/12/2021). Services & Support. A Full Range of Crime-Fighting Tools and Methods. Europol. <https://www.europol.europa.eu/operations-services-and-innovation/services-support> [Accessed: 25/06/2023].
- [7] Interpol. Criminal Intelligence Analysis. Interpol. <https://www.interpol.int/How-we-work/Criminal-intelligence-analysis2> [Accessed: 25/06/2023].
- [8] NIFC. NATO Intelligence Fusion Centre. NIFC. <https://web.ifc.bices.org/> [Accessed: 25/06/2023].
- [9] NCIA. Joint Intelligence, Surveillance and Reconnaissance. NCIA. <https://www.ncia.nato.int/what-we-do/joint-intelligence-surveillance-reconnaissance.html> [Accessed: 25/06/2023].
- [10] NATO (20/07/2022). Alliance Ground Surveillance (AGS). NATO.
- [11] NCIA. Joint Intelligence, Surveillance and Reconnaissance. NCIA. <https://www.ncia.nato.int/what-we-do/joint-intelligence-surveillance-reconnaissance.html> [Accessed: 25/06/2023].
- [12] European Union External Action (2019). Impetus 28, Magazine of the EU Military Staff, EEAS, Brussels – Autumn/Winter 2019, Issue 28. European Union External Action. https://www.eeas.europa.eu/sites/default/files/documents/eums_impetus_28_final_web.pdf [Accessed: 25/06/2023].
- [13] UK Ministry of Defence (2023). UK Terminology. Supplement to NATO Term (Joint Doctrine Publication 0-01.1). UK Ministry of Defence.

- https://assets.publishing.service.gov.uk/government/uploads/system/uploads/attachment_data/file/1138055/20230220-JDP_0_01_1_2023_Edition_A.pdf [Accessed: 26/06/2023].
- [14] Sistema di Informazione per la Sicurezza della Repubblica. L'Intelligence. Sistema di Informazione per la Sicurezza della Repubblica. <https://www.sicurezza.italiana.gov.it/sisr.nsf/cosa-facciamo/l-intelligence.html> [Accessed: 26/06/2023].
- [15] NATO Terminology Office. IMINT. NATOTerm (Official NATO Terminology Database). <https://nso.nato.int/natoterm/content/nato/pages/home.html?lg=en> [Accessed: 26/06/2023].
- [16] EDA (2017). REACT 2. EDA. <https://eda.europa.eu/what-we-do/all-activities/activities-search/react-2> [Accessed: 26/06/2023].
- [17] NATO Terminology Office. IMINT. NATOTerm (Official NATO Terminology Database). <https://nso.nato.int/natoterm/content/nato/pages/home.html?lg=en> [Accessed: 26/06/2023].
- [18] Joint Research Centre. Earth Observation. EU Science Hub (EC). https://joint-research-centre.ec.europa.eu/scientific-activities-z/earth-observation_en [Accessed: 26/06/2023].
- [19] Sky-Watch. White Paper on Image Intelligence. Sky-Watch. https://sky-watch.com/media/1537/sky-watch-white-paper-image-intelligence_rev2.pdf [Accessed: 26/06/2023].
- [20] Yonekura, E., Dolan, B., Kim, M., Grocholski, K.R., Khan, R., Kim, Y. (2022). Commercial Space Capabilities and Market Overview: The Relationship Between Commercial Space Developments and the US Department of Defense. RAND Corporation. https://www.rand.org/pubs/research_reports/RRA578-2.html [Accessed: 26/06/2023].
- [21] NASA (20/12/2022). New AI Algorithms Streamline Data Processing for Space-Based Instruments. NASA. <https://science.nasa.gov/technology/highlights/new-ai-algorithms-streamline-data-processing-for-space-based-instruments> [Accessed: 26/06/2023].
- [22] Mastelic, T., Lorincz, J., Ivandic, I., Boban, M. (2020). Aerial Imagery Based on Commercial Flights as Remote Sensing Platform. *Sensors*, 20(6):1658. <https://doi.org/10.3390/s20061658>.
- [23] Backes, D.J., Teferle, F.N. (2020). Multiscale Integration of High-Resolution Spaceborne and Drone-Based Imagery for a High-Accuracy Digital Elevation Model over Tristan da Cunha. *Frontiers in Earth Science*, 8, 319. <https://doi.org/10.3389/feart.2020.00319>.
- [24] Thenkabil, P.S. (2015). Remotely Sensed Data Characterization, Classification, and Accuracies. CRC Press. <https://doi.org/10.1201/b19294>.
- [25] Filippo Daffinà, F., Stahl, T., Quattrociochi, D., Zavagli, M., Chesworth, S., Migliorini, R., Sear, G. (2019). Aggregated Risk Assessment from Multi-Source Data Fusion. Centre for Maritime Research and Experimentation (NATO). <https://www.cmre.nato.int/msaw-2019-home/msaw2019-papers/1400-msaw2019-daffina-aggregatedriskassessmentfrommultisourcedatafusion/file> [Accessed: 27/06/2023].
- [26] NATO Terminology Office. SIGINT. NATOTerm (Official NATO Terminology Database). <https://nso.nato.int/natoterm/content/nato/pages/home.html?lg=en> [Accessed: 28/06/2023].
- [27] US Army (26/09/2019). Broad Agency Announcement (BBA) Intelligence and Information Warfare Directorate (I2WD) 2019. US Army. https://imlive.s3.amazonaws.com/Federal%20Government/ID101232736159289524839747053074899901468/BAA_I2WD_-_26_August_2019.pdf [Accessed: 28/06/2023].
- [28] NATO (2016). Allied Joint Doctrine for Signals Intelligence (AJP-2.4). NSO. <https://nso.nato.int/nso/nsdd/main/standards?search=sigint> [Accessed: 29/06/2023].
- [29] Bernard, R.L. (2009). Electronic Intelligence (ELINT) at NSA. Center for Cryptologic History (NSA). <https://www.nsa.gov/portals/75/documents/about/cryptologic-heritage/historical-figures-publications/publications/misc/elint.pdf> [Accessed: 29/06/2023].
- [30] Robinson, N., Potoglou, D., Kim, C.W., Burge, P., Warnes, R. (2010). Security at What Cost? Quantifying Trade-Offs across Liberty, Privacy and Security. RAND Corporation. https://www.rand.org/pubs/research_briefs/RB9535.html [Accessed: 29/06/2023].
- [31] Richardson, D. (24/10/2020). The Art of Electronic Eavesdropping. European Security & Defence. <https://euro-sd.com/2020/09/headline/18843/the-art-of-electronic-eavesdropping/> [Accessed: 30/06/2023].
- [32] Doerry, A.W. (2016). Comments on Airborne ISR Radar Utilization. Proceedings Photo-Optical Instrumentation Engineers (SPIE) 9829, Radar Sensor Technology XX, 98291M. <https://doi.org/10.1117/12.2214517>.
- [33] NATO Terminology Office. ELINT. NATOTerm (Official NATO Terminology Database). <https://nso.nato.int/natoterm/content/nato/pages/home.html?lg=en> [Accessed: 28/06/2023].
- [34] Chinino, G. Electronic Intelligence (ELINT). EMSopedia. <https://www.emsopedia.org/entries/electronic-intelligence-elint/> [Accessed: 29/06/2023].
- [35] Burns, T.L. (1990). The Origins of the National Security Agency, 1940-1952 (United States Cryptologic History Series V, Early Postwar Period, Volume 1). Center for Cryptologic History (NSA). <https://nsarchive2.gwu.edu/NSAEBB/NSAEBB278/02.PDF> [Accessed: 29/06/2023].
- [36] IBM X-Force Research (2017). The Weaponization of IoT Devices: Rise of the Thingbots. IBM. <https://www.ibm.com/downloads/cas/6MLEALKV> [Accessed: 29/06/2023].
- [37] Privacy International (22/02/2018). Phone Monitoring. Privacy International. <https://privacyinternational.org/explainer/1640/phone-monitoring> [Accessed: 30/06/2023].
- [38] Council of the European Union (1995). Council Resolution of 17 January 1995 on the Lawful Interception of Telecommunications (96/C 329/01). Official Journal of the European Communities. <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=OJ:C:1996:329:FULL> [Accessed: 30/06/2023].
- [39] Dabrowski, A., Petzl, G., Weipp, E.R. (2016). The Messenger Shoots Back: Network Operator Based IMSI Catcher Detection?. In 19th International Symposium on Research in Attacks, Intrusions and Defenses (RAID 2016). http://dx.doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-45719-2_13.
- [40] Purpura, P.P. (2013). Topics of Concern. In Security and Loss Prevention (Sixth Edition). Elsevier, 589-635. <https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-12-387846-5.00018-8>.
- [41] ETSI (2006). Lawful Interception (LI). Handover Interface for the Lawful Interception of Telecommunications Traffic. ETSI. https://www.etsi.org/deliver/etsi_es/201600_201699/201671/03.01.01_50/es_201671v030101m.pdf [Accessed: 30/06/2023].
- [42] Bursztein, E. (2017). Understanding the Prevalence of Web Traffic Interception. EliE. <https://elie.net/blog/security/understanding-the-prevalence-of-web-traffic-interception/> [Accessed: 30/06/2023]